

Designing Children's Book as an Educative Visual Media on Diversity and Tolerance

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ABSTRACT: Many cases of intolerance in the general public are a concern and also an inspiration for the creation of educational media for the new generation to be able to understand simple examples of tolerance so that later it can be applied in everyday life. This research aims to design an educational children's picture book about the beauty of diversity and how children can embrace differences as a form of tolerance. This book combines pictures and texts as a storytelling method. The research uses quantitative and qualitative approaches and the data obtained from literature studies and response statistics based on the survey on children in the year 5 to 6 in Citra Alam elementary school. The children's book's story contents raise the topic of a simple form of tolerance, solutions when children are faced with disagreements and how they can embrace differences in everyday life.

KEYWORDS: diversity, tolerance, children's book, illustrations, educational

I. INTRODUCTION

Tolerance in language means tolerance. In terms of tolerance, it means respecting and respecting differences between fellow human beings (Kemdikbud, 2019). Tolerance is an important trait because everyone will definitely be met with diversity. In this world there are many varieties of ethnic groups and their cultures and beliefs, including in Indonesia itself. Based on the BPS census, the number of tribes in Indonesia reached 300 ethnic groups, which were then divided into 1,340 ethnic groups (Detik, 2020). Diversity in Indonesia itself is very much and not limited to ethnic groups and ethnicities. There are beliefs, thoughts, social classes. This can certainly be an inspiration for the creation of educational media for the formation of children's character.

A child who is emotionally intelligent, characterful, and tolerant of differences will certainly find it easier to establish relationships and expand his connections when he grows up. This is supported by Aulia Fitria (2019) at the IDN Research Institute who explained the results of research on the tolerance level of the millennial generation, there is the highest tolerance data of only 28% tolerance of differences of thought, 26% of social tolerance, 18% of religious tolerance, and 14% for the level of tolerance of sex and racial. From the results of this research, it can be concluded that the level of tolerance of the younger generation in Indonesia is still relatively low. The Katadata article (2021) says that tolerance refers to the nature of respect between people, a trait that is necessary in character building. This is learned so that in the future they can easily adapt when they are in a more diverse social environment, but if a person already has a tolerant nature, tolerance education will switch functions so that someone can uphold his tolerance trait. There are various kinds of character building, such as the ability to empathise, sympathise, and tolerance.

Character building through learning about tolerance should be done early. This is evidenced by a study on the speed at which children learn new things conducted by Dr. Alison Gopnik, a professor of psychology at UC Berkeley along with NYU cognitive scientist Emily Liquin. They conducted a game-based scientific experiment to test whether children's drive to explore more than adults influenced the way they learned. Of the 64 children aged 4-5 and 87 adults, results show adults often jump to quicker conclusions, while children are

more willing to explore and gather more information before they decide on an outcome (NYPost, 2021). This proves how important it is to introduce and educate the nature of tolerance early on because children are easier to explore and learn something than when they grow up.

The importance of educating through the introduction of tolerance can be done anywhere such as school, play environment, or through the family environment at home. Picture storybooks can certainly be an educational media choice that is easy to find and use for parents in the process of building a child's tolerant character. Character building of children through tolerance education, so that the level of tolerance of children can be increased from an early age through this entitled "Jika Seluruh Dunia Seragam" Picture Book.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 The Meaning of Tolerance and Diversity

2.1.1 The meaning of Tolerance

In terms of tolerance, it means to accept and respect differences between fellow human beings (Kemdikbud, 2019).

2.1.2 The Meaning of Diversity

Diversity is a condition in society where there are many differences in various fields. These differences include ethnicity, race, religion, and intergroup. Diversity in Indonesia is influenced by various factors, namely the strategic location of Indonesia's territory, the condition of archipelagic countries, differences in natural conditions, the state of transportation and communication, public acceptance of changes (Kemdikbud, 2020).

2.2 Definition of Visual Media

According to Arief S.Sadiman, visual-based learning media is a learning media that channels messages through the sense of sight (Gunawan H, 2012: 43). There are various types of visual media. Visual media in printed media can be found in the form of posters, brochures, books, magazines, and newspapers. In non-print media, visual media can be found in the form of videos, films, web comics, social media and others.

2.3 The Importance of Tolerance Education

Tolerance education should be carried out from an early age. This is because early childhood is an excellent learning time. This is evidenced by a study conducted by Dr. Alison Gopnik, a professor of psychology at UC Berkeley along with NYU cognitive scientist Emily Liquin. Reporting from the NYPost, They conducted a game-based scientific experiment to test whether children's drive to explore more than adults affects the way they learn. Of the 64 children aged 4-5 and 87 adults, results show adults often jump to quicker conclusions, while children are more willing to explore and gather more information before they decide on an outcome. This shows that children when learning tend to focus more on the process than the final result. Therefore, recognition and learning through a situation or story such as in a children's book is the right option in addition to advice.

III. METHODOLOGY

Research methodology are procedures or scientific steps taken to be able to obtain the data needed to fulfill research objectives. The research method itself is divided into 2, namely qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative research method is a research method to examine the observation and observation of an object. Quantitative research is a research method based on explorations of numeric patterns collected from respondents' answers.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Illustrated Storybooks as Educational Media with Companions

At each level of reading children have their own challenges and obstacles. However, children with a "fluent reader" level (equivalent to grades 4-6 of elementary school) are generally able to read sentences in full. Unfortunately, this does not rule out the possibility that some who have learning difficulties or who have low

literacy levels will experience reading barriers. Parents and teachers can certainly contribute to helping children train their reading skills while improving their child's literacy by conducting reading guidance.

4.2 Sekolah Citra Alam as a research location and institution receiving book distribution

Sekolah Citra Alam is a nature-based inclusive private school foundation that focuses on educating each of its students to have a caring and leadership spirit by studying, exploring, and preserving the environment and God's creations in it so that students can later spread benefits to the environment. The foundation has schools from playgroups and Kindergarten to High School levels. The school uses a national curriculum and is complemented by a variety of international curricula and self-developed nature curricula. Sekolah Citra Alam applies learning through real experiences, in addition to classroom learning, this school also implements outdoor activities including Outing, camping, Market Day, Year-End Parties, and various extracurricular activities. Because Sekolah Citra Alam is also an inclusive school, this school has a special department that handles children with special needs, namely the inclusion department.

4.3 Illustration Concept

The word Illustration comes from the Latin *Illustrare*, which means to explain or explain, thus an illustrative image is defined as an image that simultaneously serves to explain a narrative or event (Kemdikbud, 2019). Based on this explanation, it can be concluded that the illustration must be able to describe or explain a character and narrative of the conditions of an event.

Character Design

Character design for this book consists of two main characters with different genders and racial background as a form of inclusivity towards diversity.

*Picture 4.1 Binar dan Kala
Character Design*

Typography

For typography, the text on the cover will use lettering that has been adjusted to the visual cover of the book as the headline and the subheadline will be adjusted to the font with the content of the book, namely the Andika New Basic font. This font is a standard font criterion used by the Ministry of Education and Culture in writing the contents of children's books annual project Gerakan Literasi Nasional (GLN).

Gambar 4.2 Andika New Basic
Font Samples

Colour Palette

Berdasarkan survey selera pembaca terhadap gaya gambar yang menarik bagi mereka rata-rata memilih gambar dengan palet warna hangat namun dengan kontras yang tinggi (untuk membedakan komposisi jarak).

Picture 4.3 Colour Palette Used

Layout

The layouts that will be used in this illustrated storybook visualisation are spots, frames, and spreads. As well as the placement of text that is adjusted to the illustrative flow so that it makes it easier for children to enjoy the storyline through illustrations inside the book.

Picture 4.4 Layout Reference
(Sumber : www.pinterest.com)

Final Artwork

The finished artwork size is 20x20 cm book binded with staples. The book may be distributed by partners soon such as Sekolah Citra Alam.

Picture 4.5 Final Spread Illustration Sample

(Source : Personal Artwork)

V. CONCLUSION

The design of this illustrated storybook is intended so that children as the next generation of the nation can become tolerant individuals who can embrace differences as diversity. The story in this book gives a very simple example of differences so that children more easily understand the concept of appreciating differences, which is about differences in tastes. This is done so that children can understand if respecting peers is also part of tolerance.

Based on the results of respondents from research related to prototype trials that have been carried out by the author on students in grades 5 and 6 of elementary school, it shows that children are enthusiastic about reading the entire story in the picture storybook that has been designed.

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